

Emergence of Melanoma by replicating ultraviolet DNA photos

Alireza Sepehri

Independent Researcher

Abstract:

Background:

Up to date, it has been known that ultraviolet rays could cause to melanoma and other cancers; however, its mechanism isn't clear yet.

Aim: In this article, we show that short and high energetic waves like ultraviolet take the shape of DNA bases and image their features in a liquid within the nucleus. Then, these DNA photos are replicated and some extra DNAs are emerged. These new DNAs produce extra cells. These extra cells could be the main cause of melanoma and other cancers.

Material: This is a theoretical model which is compared with experiments. Needed material in theory are: 1. Mathematics 2. Excel softwares 3. Growth rate of melanoma 4. Electromagnetic waves 5. Skin cells

Method:

1. First, we introduce an action for producing DNA photos by electromagnetic waves.
2. Then, we obtain the Hamiltonian and momentum densities of DNA photos.
3. Next, we obtain the relation between the size of DNA photos , number of photons or waves and the frequency .
4. After that, we calculate the number of microstates of DNA photos
5. Finally, we obtain the probability for producing extra cells and tumors in terms of wavelengths and intensities

Results:

1. Short waves like ultraviolet rays take photos of DNAs. This means that they take shapes of DNA bases and image them in a liquid around the DNA.

2. These photos are replicated by DNA polymerases and extra DNAs are produced.
3. These extra DNAs produce melanoma and some other cancers
4. The size of tumors depend on the number of photons.
5. The probability for producing cancer depends on the wavelength and by its reduction , increases.

Conclusions:

Some short wavelengths like ultraviolet rays could penetrate the cell and nuclear membranes, take shape of DNA bases within the nucleus and image their photos on the liquid. These images are replicated and produce extra DNAs and cells. These cells are the main cause of cancer. There is a direct relation between wavelength and the probability for producing cancer. This model is in agreement with observations.

Keywords: Melanoma, DNA, Image, Photo, Replication, Ultraviolet

I.Introduction

One of dangerous disease which has a direct effect on the human's life is the melanoma. This cancer could take beauty and healthy of patient and lead them to death. For this reason, many scientists are working on this subject and try to find a solution for it. Most investigations show that the origin of this cancer could be ultraviolet rates. For example, some authors have discussed the mechanisms of UV damage induction, the genomic distribution of this damage, relevant DNA repair mechanisms, the proposed mechanisms of how UV-induced CPDs bring about DNA replication-dependent mutagenicity in mammalian cells, and the strong signature of UV damage and mutagenesis found in skin cancer genomes [1]. In other article, some investigators have argued that ultraviolet radiation (UVR) have a direct mutational role in inducing or promoting melanoma formation. They have described relevant mouse models and discussed how these models can best be translated to the study of human skin and cutaneous melanoma [2]. In other research, some authors have shown that E26 transformation-specific transcription factor induce a unique Ultraviolet (UV) damage signature that drives recurrent mutagenesis in melanoma [3]. In other study, it has been shown that there is a convergence of some genetic changes in mucosal melanomas between species

and some distinctly different paths to tumorigenesis [4]. In other work, authors analyzed physical drug delivery enhancement technologies with a focus on improving UV damaged skin, actinic keratoses and non-melanoma skin cancer treatment [5]. In other research, it has been argued that high birth weight and high early-life UV exposure may be important independent risk factors for melanoma diagnosis before age 30. Also, it has been shown that adopting skin-protective behaviors as early as infancy could be important for primary prevention of melanoma in younger people [6]. In other article, authors have argued that Oxidative stress and DNA damage caused by ultraviolet light (UV) are major causative factors of melanoma formation. They have attempted to reveal the pathogenesis of melanoma and screen new biomarkers by constructing a TF-mRNA-miRNA axis [7]. In another investigations, authors demonstrated an important function of the vitamin D endocrine system (VDES) for prevention of basal cell carcinoma, squamous cell carcinoma and melanoma and identified the vitamin D receptor as a tumor suppressor in the skin [8]. Motivated by these researches, we propose a new model which considers the process of producing melanoma by ultraviolet rays. In this model, electromagnetic waves take photos from DNAs and image them in material around them. Then, these photos are replicated and produce extra DNAs and cells. These cells could be the main reason of melanoma.

The outline of article as follows: In section II, we propose a model and consider the process of formation of DNA bases by ultraviolet rays. In section III, we propose results of the model. In section IV, we discuss about results. Section V devoted to conclusion.

II. Method: Emergence of extra DNA bases by replicating of DNA photos

When high energetic waves like ultraviolet rays achieve to cells, pass the membranes and interact with DNAs. They take photos of DNA bases and image them on the liquid around it. These DNA photos have structures like the hexagonal/pentagonal structures of DNA bases (See figure 1). These DNA photos are replicated by polymerases and some extra DNA bases are emerged (See figure 2). We can formulate this process and obtain number of extra states within cells.

These extra DNA states produce extra cells. These extra cells can cause the main cause of melanoma and other cancers.

To begin, we introduce the action of hexagonal DNA photos:

$$S_{hexa} = \int d^3 l_h \sqrt{\eta^{ab} g_{\mu\nu} \partial_a \psi^{\mu\uparrow} \Psi^{M\downarrow} \partial_b \psi^{\nu\downarrow} \Psi^{M\uparrow} + 2\pi \tilde{l}_h^2 H(F)} \quad (1)$$

Where $\psi^{\mu\uparrow} \Psi^{M\downarrow}$ are coupled atoms in hexagonal bases, $g_{\mu\nu}$ is the metric within a DNA, $\mu, \nu = 1 \dots 6$, η^{ab} is the metric within a cell, $a, b = 1..3$, l_h is the separation distance between two atoms within a hexagonal base and:

$$H(F) = \sum_{i=1}^6 \frac{-(F_1 \dots F_i)}{i! \lambda} \quad (2)$$

$$F = F_{\mu\nu} F^{\mu\nu} \quad (3)$$

$$F_{\mu\nu} = \partial_\mu \tilde{A}_\nu - \partial_\nu \tilde{A}_\mu \quad (4)$$

Where $F_{\mu\nu}$ is the electromagnetic fields strength and \tilde{A}_ν is the electromagnetic vector. On the other hand, the action of pentagonal molecule is:

$$S_{penta} = \int d^3 l_p \sqrt{\eta^{ab} g_{\mu\nu} \partial_a \psi^{\mu\uparrow} \Psi^{M\downarrow} \partial_b \psi^{\nu\downarrow} \Psi^{M\uparrow} + 2\pi \tilde{l}_p^2 P(F)} \quad (5)$$

Where l_p is the separation distance between two atoms within a pentagonal base and

$$P(F) = \sum_{i=1}^5 \frac{(F_1 \dots F_i)}{i! \lambda} \quad (6)$$

$$F = F_{\mu\nu} F^{\mu\nu} \quad (7)$$

$$F_{\mu\nu} = \partial_\mu A_\nu - \partial_\nu A_\mu \quad (8)$$

Above actions give the below momentum densities:

$$\mathbb{I}\mathbb{I}\mathbb{I}_h = \frac{2\pi\tilde{l}_h^2 H'(F)F_{01}}{\sqrt{\eta^{ab}g_{\mu\nu}\partial_a\psi^{\mu\uparrow}\Psi^{M\downarrow}\partial_b\psi^{\nu\downarrow}\Psi^{M\uparrow} + 2\pi\tilde{l}_h^2 H(F)}} \quad (9)$$

$$\mathbb{I}\mathbb{I}\mathbb{I}_p = \frac{2\pi\tilde{l}_p^2 P'(F)F_{01}}{\sqrt{\eta^{ab}g_{\mu\nu}\partial_a\psi^{\mu\uparrow}\Psi^{M\downarrow}\partial_b\psi^{\nu\downarrow}\Psi^{M\uparrow} + 2\pi\tilde{l}_p^2 P(F)}} \quad (10)$$

Where $\mathbb{I}\mathbb{I}\mathbb{I}_h$ is the hexagonal momentum density and $\mathbb{I}\mathbb{I}\mathbb{I}_p$ is the pentagonal momentum density. Using above momentum densities and actions, we can obtain below Hamiltonians [9-11]:

$$H_{hexa} = \int d^3 l_h \mathbb{I}\mathbb{I}\mathbb{I}_h \partial_t \tilde{A}_1 - L = \int d l_h [l_h^2 \mathbb{I}\mathbb{I}\mathbb{I}_h F_{01} - \partial_t (l_h^2 \mathbb{I}\mathbb{I}\mathbb{I}_h) \tilde{A}_0] - L_{hexa} \quad (11)$$

$$H_{penta} = \int d^3 l_p \mathbb{I}\mathbb{I}\mathbb{I}_p \partial_t \tilde{A}_1 - L = \int d l_p [l_p^2 \mathbb{I}\mathbb{I}\mathbb{I}_p F_{01} - \partial_t (l_p^2 \mathbb{I}\mathbb{I}\mathbb{I}_p) \tilde{A}_0] - L_{penta} \quad (12)$$

Where $H_{hexa/penta}$ are Hamiltonians and $L_{hexa/penta}$ are Lagrangians. Assuming $\partial_t(l_h^2 \mathbb{I}\mathbb{I}\mathbb{I}_h) = 0$ and $\partial_t(l_p^2 \mathbb{I}\mathbb{I}\mathbb{I}_p)$, we obtain:

$$\mathbb{I}\mathbb{I}\mathbb{I}_h = \frac{K_h^2}{l_h^2} \quad (13)$$

$$\mathbb{I}\mathbb{I}\mathbb{I}_p = \frac{K_p^2}{l_p^2} \quad (14)$$

Using equations (9,10,13,14), we obtain:

$$l_h = \left[\frac{K_h^2 \sqrt{\eta^{ab}g_{\mu\nu}\partial_a\psi^{\mu\uparrow}\Psi^{M\downarrow}\partial_b\psi^{\nu\downarrow}\Psi^{M\uparrow} + 2\pi\tilde{l}_h^2 H(F)}}{2\pi\tilde{l}_h^2 H'(F)F_{01}} \right]^{1/2} \quad (15)$$

$$l_p = \left[\frac{K_p^2 \sqrt{\eta^{ab}g_{\mu\nu}\partial_a\psi^{\mu\uparrow}\Psi^{M\downarrow}\partial_b\psi^{\nu\downarrow}\Psi^{M\uparrow} + 2\pi\tilde{l}_p^2 P(F)}}{2\pi\tilde{l}_p^2 P'(F)F_{01}} \right]^{1/2} \quad (16)$$

Above lengths are separation distances between atoms within hexagonal and pentagonal DNA photos. These distances depend on the electromagnetic fields. These fields divide into electrical (E) and magnetic (B) fields. On the other hand, these fields have direct relation with frequency of photons ($h\nu$). We can write:

$$F = F_{\mu\nu}F^{\mu\nu} \simeq [E^2 + B^2] \simeq 2\mu_0 \tilde{p} \simeq 2\mu_0 n h \nu \quad (17)$$

Where \tilde{p} is the power density, E and B are electrical and magnetical fields, μ_0 is the magnetic constant, n is the number of photons/fields and ν is the frequency of photons/fields. Using equation (17), we can rewrite equations (2 and 6) as below:

$$H(F) = \sum_{i=1}^6 \frac{[2\mu_0 n h]^i (v_1 \dots v_i)}{i! \lambda} \quad (18)$$

$$P(F) = \sum_{i=1}^5 \frac{[2\mu_0 n h]^i (v_1 \dots v_i)}{i! \lambda} \quad (19)$$

Usually, couplings between atoms is very weaker than coupling between fields. Thus, we can write:

$$\eta^{ab} g_{\mu\nu} \partial_a \psi^{\mu\uparrow} \Psi^{M\downarrow} \partial_b \psi^{\nu\downarrow} \Psi^{M\uparrow} \ll 2\pi \tilde{l}_h^2 H(F) \quad (20)$$

$$\eta^{ab} g_{\mu\nu} \partial_a \psi^{\mu\uparrow} \Psi^{M\downarrow} \partial_b \psi^{\nu\downarrow} \Psi^{M\uparrow} \ll 2\pi \tilde{l}_p^2 P(F) \quad (21)$$

Using equations (18-21), we can rewrite equations (15 and 16):

$$l_h = \left[\frac{K_h^2 \sqrt{2\pi \tilde{l}_h^2 \sum_{i=1}^6 \frac{[2\mu_0 n h]^i (v_1 \dots v_i)}{i! \lambda}}}{2\pi \tilde{l}_h^2 \sum_{i=1}^5 \frac{[2\mu_0 n h]^{i-1} (v_1 \dots v_{i-1})}{(i-1)! \lambda}} \right]^{1/2} \quad (22)$$

$$l_p = \left[\frac{K_p^2 \sqrt{2\pi \tilde{l}_p^2 \sum_{i=1}^5 \frac{[2\mu_0 n h]^i (v_1 \dots v_i)}{i! \lambda}}}{2\pi \tilde{l}_p^2 \sum_{i=1}^4 \frac{[2\mu_0 n h]^{i-1} (v_1 \dots v_{i-1})}{(i-1)! \lambda}} \right]^{1/2} \quad (23)$$

Using above lengths, we can define the area of hexagonal and pentagonal photos as:

$$A_{HEXA} \sim 6l_h^2 \sin\left(\frac{\pi}{6} - 2\theta_{HEXA}\right) \quad (24)$$

$$A_{PENTA} \sim 6l_p^2 \sin\left(\frac{\pi}{6} - 2\theta_{PENTA}\right) \quad (25)$$

Total area of a DNA photo could be derived by summing over areas of all hexagonal/pentagonal bases:

$$A_{DNA-photo} \sim \prod_{j=1}^J \left[\sum_{l=1}^L \left[1 + A_{HEXA,l,j} + A_{PENTA,l,j} \right] \sum_{m=1}^M \left[1 + A_{HEXA,m,j} + A_{PENTA,m,j} \right] \right] \quad (26)$$

Previously, it has been shown that area has a direct relation with the entropy [12]:

$$\tilde{S} \sim Y [A_{DNA-photo}]^\beta \quad (27)$$

Where Y and β are some constants. On the other hand, this entropy has a direct relation with number of microstates ($\Omega_{DNA-photo}$):

$$\tilde{S} \sim K_B \log(\Omega_{DNA-photo}) \quad (28)$$

Thus, number of microstates of a DNA photo which is produced by electromagnetic fields could be obtained from below equation:

$$\Omega_{DNA-photo} \sim e^{\frac{Y[A_{DNA-photo}]^\beta}{K_B}} \quad (29)$$

Using this number of microstate, we can calculate the probability for producing extra DNA states:

$$P = \Omega_{DNA-photo} / \Omega_{DNA} \quad (30)$$

Where $\Omega_{DNA-photo}$ is the number of microstates of DNA photos which are produced by electromagnetic fields and Ω_{DNA} is total number of microstates of a DNA. This probability increases by increasing number of photons and decreasing wavelengths of electromagnetic waves.

Fig1. Ultraviolet rays take some photos of DNA bases.

Fig 2. DNA photos are replicated and extra DNAs are emerged.

III. Results: Testing the model against data

DNA photos could have the main role in producing extra cells. These cells are the main cause of some cancers like the melanoma. Thus, there is a direct relation between the probability for producing DNA photos and tumor size.

$$Tu \sim \eta P_{DNA-photo} = \eta \Omega_{DNA-photo} / \Omega_{DNA} \quad (32)$$

Where Tu is the tumor size and η is a constant. In figure 3, we show the growth of tumor size for different wave intensities in terms of time. For lower intensities, the velocity of growth is less than large intensities. This is because that by increasing wave intensities, more photons are emitted. These photons take some photos of DNAs and image them within liquid. Then, these DNA photos are replicated and new DNAs are produced. These extra DNAs produce extra cells and cancer.

Fig 3. Tumour sizes for different wave intensity in terms of time.

Pink, red, blue, green are corresponded to $n=10000, 20000, 30000, 40000$.

In figure 4, we show the probability for producing tumor in terms of intensity's number. It is clear that by increasing number of photons, number of DNA photos are increased. These DNA photos could be the main cause of melanoma and other cancers.

Fig 4. Probability for producing tumor in terms of intensity's number

In figure 5, we show the probability for producing DNA tumours in terms of wavelength. It is clear that by reducing wavelengths and increasing frequencies, waves become more shorter and can penetrate the nuclear membranes. These waves interact with DNA bases and take some images from them. These images are replicated by polymerases and produce extra DNA bases.

Fig 5. Probability for producing tumour in terms of wavelength

IV. Discussion

This article has some interesting results. According to calculations and figures, waves with low frequencies and long lengths couldn't pass the nuclear and cell membranes and have no role in producing melanoma and other tumors. For example, radio waves have no effects on the skin cells. However, by increasing frequencies or decreasing wavelengths, waves could pass the nuclear and cell

membranes and take some copies from DNA bases. These copies are imaged on the liquid or materials around a DNA. These copies could be replicated and some new DNA bases are emerged.

V. Conclusion

In this research, we have proposed a model which considers the process of formation of cancer by ultraviolet rays and other electromagnetic fields. We have shown that waves with low frequency couldn't pass the cell and nuclear membranes and have no any role in producing cancer. However, by reducing wavelength and increasing frequency, waves could pass the nuclear membranes and interact with DNAs. Then, these waves take some photos of DNA bases and image them on the material within the nucleus. Next, polymerases help to replicate these DNA images and produce new DNAs. These extra DNAs produce extra cells and cancer. The size of tumor depends on the wavelength and number of photons or waves which are attracted by DNAs within the nucleus.

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